

COST OF CULTIVATION OF BLACK GRAM IN BULDHANA DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

Mayuri Phuke*, R D Vaidkar**, U T Dangore**, and N V Shende***

*PG student-Deptt of Agril Econ & stat, PGI, Dr PDKV Akola

**Asstt Professor- Deptt of Agril Econ & stat, PGI, Dr PDKV Akola

***Professor & Head- Deptt of Agril Econ & stat, PGI, Dr PDKV Akola
PGI, DR PDKV Akola, Maharashtra, India.

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Abstract

A schedule was designed for primary data collection by keeping objectives of the study, in view. The data pertains for the year 2024-25 and it was collected through personal interview of farmers. The economics of black gram production was calculated by using standard cost concept. At overall level, the per hectare cost of production at cost 'A₁', cost 'A₂', cost 'B₁', cost 'B₂', cost 'C₁', cost 'C₂', cost 'C₃' were Rs.32103.25, Rs. 32103.25, Rs. 33007.50, Rs. 47769.39, Rs. 35268.64, Rs. 50030.53 and Rs. 55033.58 respectively. The major share of cost of cultivation goes towards cost 'A₁' (58.33 per cent). In cost A₁ share of hired labour was 13.31 per cent, machine charges 11.37 per cent, bullock labour 8.62 per cent, fertilizer 3.75 per cent, seed 3.30 per cent, plant protection 1.87 per cent indicating that, all the above inputs are cash inputs for which farmers required to pay immediately from his pocket. The per hectare yield obtained by overall farmers was 12.96 quintals with gross return of Rs. 88961.33 The per hectare cost obtained by overall farmers was Rs. 4206.38 per quintals.

Keyword: Black gram, cost of cultivation**Introduction**

Black gram is one of the important pulse crops of the kharif season in our country. It belongs to the family Leguminaceae and sub-family Papilionaceae. The earlier name of black gram was Phaseolus mungo, which has now been changed to Vigna mungo. It is most commonly used in Punjabi cuisine and is known as maah di daal in the local language of Punjab.

The most commonly used Improved Varieties of Black gram in India are Tirupati mimumu-1(A.P.), Co-6(TN), VBN-6(TN), MDU-1(TN), TAU-1 (PDKV), AKU-15 (PDKV), AKU-10-1(PDKV) also called as blackgold ,Phule Vasu, Phule Rajan, VBN 9-10, PDU-1, Vishwas (NUL-7) and SUG-1190.

Objective

To measure the cost and returns of black gram cultivators.

Methodology

A schedule was designed for primary data collection by keeping objectives of the study, in view. The data pertains for the year 2024-25 and it was collected through personal interview of farmers. The economics of black gram production was calculated by using standard cost concept

Result & Discssion**Per hectare cost of cultivation of black gram**

To workout gross returns at various cost concepts, to workout Benefit-Cost ratio and to workout net returns over various cost it is necessary to workout cost of cultivation of black gram. The per hectare average cost incurred on the production of black gram for small, medium, large groups and overall level has been worked out and presented .Per hectare cost of cultivation of black gram grown by the small farmers is presented in Table 1.

It is revealed that from the Table 1 that the per hectare cost of production at cost 'A₁', cost 'A₂', cost 'B₁', cost 'B₂', cost 'C₁', cost 'C₂' and cost 'C₃' were Rs.31514.12, Rs.31514.12, Rs.32781.98, Rs.47678.58, Rs.36013.78, Rs.50910.38 and Rs.56001.42 respectively. The major share of cost of cultivation goes towards cost 'A₁' (56.27 per cent). In cost A₁ share of hired labour was 13.31 per cent, bullock labour 10.62 per cent, machine charges 9.86 per cent, fertilizer 4.37 per cent, seed 3.32 per cent, plant protection 2.00 per cent, indicating that, all the above inputs are cash inputs for which farmers required to pay immediately from his pocket. The per hectare yield obtained by small farmers was 12.94 quintals with gross return of Rs. 89769.63. In case of small size group, the per quintal cost of production was Rs. 4289.95.

The per hectare cost of cultivation of black gram grown by the medium group farmers is presented in Table 2.

It is revealed that from the Table 2. that the per hectare cost of production at cost 'A₁', cost 'A₂', cost 'B₁', cost 'B₂', cost 'C₁', cost 'C₂', cost 'C₃' were Rs. 31100.53, Rs. 31100.53, Rs. 32209.51, Rs. 46499.06, Rs. 34269.18,

Rs. 48558.72 and Rs. 53414.59 respectively. The major share of cost

of cultivation goes towards cost 'A₁' (58.22 per cent). In cost A₁ share of hired labour was 13.72 per cent, machine charges 12.17 per cent, bullock labour 4.98 per cent, fertilizer 3.95 per cent, seed 3.28 per cent, plant protection 1.92 per cent, indicating that, all the above inputs are cash inputs for which farmers required to pay immediately from his pocket. The per hectare yield obtained by medium farmers was 12.66 quintals. With Gross return Rs. 86127.26. The per hectare cost obtained by small farmers was Rs. 4178.60 per quintals.

The per hectare cost of cultivation of black gram grown by the large group farmers is presented in Table 3.

It is revealed that from the Table 3. that the per hectare cost of production at cost 'A₁', cost 'A₂', cost 'B₁', cost 'B₂', cost 'C₁', cost 'C₂', cost 'C₃' were Rs.33237.36, Rs. 33237.36 , Rs. 33643.00, Rs. 48733.17, Rs. 35238.16 Rs.50328.33 and Rs. 55361.16 respectively, the major share of cost of cultivation goes towards cost 'A₁' (60.04 per cent). In cost A₁ share of hired labour was 13.04 per cent, machine charges 12.16 per cent, bullock labour 10.69 per cent, seed 3.30 per cent, fertilizer 2.94 per cent, plant protection 1.77 per cent indicating that, all the above inputs are cash inputs for which farmers required to pay immediately from his pocket. The per hectare yield obtained by large farmers was 13.27 quintals with Gross return Rs. 90931.01. The per hectare cost obtained by large farmers was Rs. 4130.22 per quintals.

The per hectare cost of cultivation of black gram grown by the overall group farmers is presented in Table 4

It is revealed that from the Table 4 that the per hectare cost of production at cost 'A₁', cost 'A₂', cost 'B₁', cost 'B₂', cost 'C₁', cost 'C₂', cost 'C₃' were Rs.32103.25, Rs. 32103.25, Rs. 33007.50, Rs. 47769.39, Rs. 35268.64,

Rs. 50030.53 and Rs. 55033.58 respectively. The major share of cost of cultivation goes towards cost 'A₁' (58.33 per cent). In cost A₁ share of hired labour was 13.31 per cent, machine charges 11.37 per cent, bullock labour 8.62 per cent, fertilizer 3.75 per cent, seed 3.30 per cent, plant protection 1.87 per cent indicating that, all the above inputs are cash inputs for which farmers required to pay immediately from his pocket. The per hectare yield obtained by overall farmers was 12.96 quintals with gross return of Rs. 88961.33 The per hectare cost obtained by overall farmers was Rs. 4206.38 per quintals.

Per hectare cost and returns from black gram

The cost and returns structure per hectare of Agricultural production, helps the farmer in mapping adjustment in the organization and thereby secure the optimum level of production and income. The Table 5. indicates that at overall average gross return workout to Rs. 88442.41. This means black gram crop appeared to be good from monetary benefits. The highest input output ratio at cost C₃ was recorded in large group i.e., 1.64 and the lowest input output ratio at cost C₃ was recorded in small size group. At overall level input output ratio at cost C₃ was 1.62. The input output ratio which is an indicator of economic efficiency in crop production for the crop and other discussion

indicated that black gram registered a good input output ratio 1.62 | means growing of the black gram is profitable venture.

Table 1. Per hectare cost of cultivation of small farmers

Sr. No.	Item	Unit		Input/ha.	Cost/Unit of input	Total Cost Per Ha.	% to Cost "C3"
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	5.80	230.29	1335.68	2.39
		Female	Days	27.78	220.29	6119.66	10.93
				33.58		7455.34	13.31
2	Bullock Labour		Days	5.97	996.54	5949.34	10.62
3	Machine charges		Hours	6.18	893.54	5522.08	9.86
4	Seed		Kg.	16.34	113.88	1860.80	3.32
5	Manures		QTLS.	4.21	250.00	1052.50	1.88
6	Fertilizer	N	Kg.	13.43	37.38	502.01	0.90
		P	Kg.	22.27	54.88	1222.18	2.18
		K	Kg.	11.35	48.97	555.81	0.99
		S	Kg.	3.37	50.42	169.92	0.30
				50.42		2449.92	4.37
7	Irrigation charges	(Rs.)				0.00	0.00
8	Plant Protection	(Rs.)				1120.73	2.00
9	Incidental charges	(Rs.)				450.60	0.80
10	Repairing Charges	(Rs.)				834.77	1.49
11	Working Capital (1 to 10)	(Rs.)				26696.08	47.67
12	Interest on working Capital					400.44	0.72
13	Depreciation	(Rs.)				4352.60	7.77
14	Land Revenue	(Rs.)				65.00	0.12
15	COST "A1" (Items 11 to 14)	(Rs.)				31514.12	56.27
16	Rental Value for leased Land					0.00	0.00
17	COST "A2" (Item 15 to 16)					31514.12	56.27
18	Int. on Fix. Cap. @ 10%					1267.86	2.26
19	COST "B1" (Items 17 to 18)					32781.98	58.54
20	Rental Value of owned Land					14896.60	26.60
21	COST "B2" (Items 19 to 20)					47678.58	85.14
22	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	7.74	213.52	1652.64	2.95
		Female	Days	8.66	182.35	1579.15	2.82
				16.40	395.87	3231.80	5.77
23	COST "C1"(Item 19 to 22)					36013.78	64.31
24	COST "C2"(Item 21 to 22)					50910.38	90.91
25	10% Cost C2*					5091.04	9.09
26	COST "C3"(Item 24 to 25)					56001.42	100.00
29	Yield of main produce per hectare	(Rs.)		12.94	6899.55	89280.18	
30	Value of by produce per ha.	(Rs.)		7.53	65.00	489.45	
30	Value of total produce					89769.63	
31	Per quintal cost of Production					4289.95	

Table 2. Per hectare cost of cultivation of medium farmers

SN.	I T E M	Unit		Input/ha.	Cost/Unit of input	Total Cost Per Ha.	% to Cost "C3"
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	6.82	269.21	1836.01	3.44
		Female	Days	25.63	214.38	5494.56	10.29
				32.45		7330.57	13.72
2	Bullock Labour		Days	4.93	539.47	2659.59	4.98
3	Machine charges		Hours	7.35	884.74	6502.84	12.17
4	Seed		Kg.	15.59	112.28	1750.45	3.28
5	Manures		QTLS.	7.13	250.00	1782.50	3.34
6	Fertilizer	N	Kg.	9.84	35.60	350.30	0.66
		P	Kg.	18.81	57.59	1083.27	2.03
		K	Kg.	12.80	50.40	645.12	1.21
		S	Kg.	0.58	58.26	33.79	0.06
				42.03		2112.48	3.95
7	Irrigation charges	(Rs.)				0.00	0.00
8	(Plant Protection)	(Rs.)				1026.40	1.92

9	Incidental charges	(Rs.)				366.61	0.69
10	Repairing Charges	(Rs.)				990.52	1.85
11	Working Capital (1 to 14)	(Rs.)				24521.96	45.91
12	Interest on working Capital					367.83	0.69
13	Depreciation	(Rs.)				6145.75	11.51
14	Land Revenue	(Rs.)				65.00	0.12
15	COST "A1" (Items 11 to 14)	(Rs.)				31100.53	58.22
16	Rental Value for leased Land					0.00	0.00
17	COST "A2" (Item 15 to 16)					31100.53	58.22
18	Int. on Fix.Cap. @ 10%					1108.98	2.08
19	COST "B1" (Items 15 to 18)					32209.51	60.30
20	Rental Value of owned Land					14289.54	26.75
21	COST "B2" (Items 19 to 20)					46499.06	87.05
22	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	6.01	211.75	1272.62	2.38
		Female	Days	5.13	153.42	787.04	1.47
				11.14	365.17	2059.66	3.86
23	COST "C1"(Item 19 to 22)					34269.18	64.16
24	COST "C2"(Item 21 to 22)					48558.72	90.91
25	10% Cost C2*					4855.87	9.09
26	COST "C3"(Item 24 to 25)					53414.59	100.00
29	Yield of main produce per hectare	(Rs.)		12.66	6762.54	85613.76	
30	Value of By-produce per ha.	(Rs.)		7.90	65.00	513.50	
30	Value of total produce					86127.26	
31	Per quintal cost of Production					4178.60	

Table 3. Per hectare cost of cultivation of large farmers

S.N.	I T E M	Unit		Input/ha.	Cost/Unit of input	Total Cost Per Ha.	% to Cost "C3"
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	6.62	254.82	1686.91	3.05
		Female	Days	26.69	207.24	5531.24	9.99
				33.31		7218.14	13.04
2	Bullock Labour		Days	5.86	1010.34	5920.59	10.69
3	Machine charges		Hours	7.62	883.70	6733.79	12.16
4	Seed		Kg.	16.72	109.31	1827.66	3.30
5	Manures		QTLS.	9.38	250.00	2345.00	4.24
6	Fertilizer	N	Kg.	7.53	38.45	289.53	0.52
		P	Kg.	14.67	54.65	801.72	1.45
		K	Kg.	11.42	44.90	512.76	0.93
		S	Kg.	0.42	55.19	23.18	0.04
				34.04		1627.18	2.94
7	Irrigation charges	(Rs.)				0.00	0.00
9	(Plant Protection)	(Rs.)				978.05	1.77
10	Incidental charges	(Rs.)				297.07	0.54
11	Repairing Charges	(Rs.)				607.16	1.10
15	Working Capital (1 to 14)	(Rs.)				27554.66	49.77
16	Interest on working Capital					413.32	0.75
17	Depreciation	(Rs.)				5204.38	9.40
18	Land Revenue	(Rs.)				65.00	0.12
19	COST "A1" (Items 15 to 18)	(Rs.)				33237.36	60.04
20	Rental Value for leased Land					0.00	0.00
21	COST "A2" (Item 19 to 20)					33237.36	60.04
22	Int. on Fix.Cap. @ 10%					405.65	0.73
23	COST "B1" (Items 19 + 22)					33643.00	60.77
21	Rental Value of owned Land					15090.17	27.26
22	COST "B2" (Items 23 + 24)					48733.17	88.03
23	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	4.90	210.51	1031.50	1.86
		Female	Days	3.92	143.79	563.66	1.02
				8.82		1595.16	2.88
24	COST "C1"(Item 23+26)					35238.16	63.65
25	COST "C2"(Item 25+26)					50328.33	90.91
26	10% Cost C2*					5032.83	9.09
27	COST "C3"(Item 30+31)					55361.16	100.00
28	Yield of main produce per hectare	(Rs.)		13.27	6810.69	90377.86	

29	Value of By-produce/ha.	(Rs.)		8.51	65.00	553.15	
						90931.01	
30	Main Produce +By produce					90931.01	
31	Per quintal cost of Prod.					4130.22	

Table 4. Per hectare cost of cultivation of overall farmers

SN	Item	Unit		Input/h a.	Cost/Unit of input	Total Cost Per Ha.	% to Cost "C3"
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	6.41	251.44	1612.57	2.93
		Female	Days	26.70	213.97	5713.00	10.38
				33.11		7325.57	13.31
2	Bullock Labour		Days	5.59	848.78	4741.87	8.62
3	Machine charges		Hours	7.05	887.33	6255.65	11.37
4	Seed		Kg.	16.22	111.82	1813.40	3.30
5	Manures		QTLs.	6.91	250.00	1726.67	3.14
6	Fertilizer	N	Kg.	10.27	37.14	381.34	0.69
		P	Kg.	18.58	55.71	1035.22	1.88
		K	Kg.	11.86	48.09	570.19	1.04
		S	Kg.	1.46	54.62	79.57	0.14
				42.16		2066.31	3.75
7	Irrigation charges	(Rs.)				0.00	0.00
9	(Plant Protection)	(Rs.)				1027.96	1.87
10	Incidental charges	(Rs.)				359.16	0.65
11	Repairing Charges	(Rs.)				833.52	1.51
14	Weedicide	(Rs.)				0.00	0.00
15	Working Capital (1 to 14)	(Rs.)				26150.11	47.52
16	Interest on working Capital					392.25	0.71
17	Depreciation	(Rs.)				5495.89	9.99
18	Land Revenue	(Rs.)				65.00	0.12
19	COST "A1" (Items 15 to 18)	(Rs.)				32103.25	58.33
20	Rental Value for leased Land					0.00	0.00
21	COST "A2" (Item 19 to 20)					32103.25	58.33
22	Int. on Fix. Cap. @ 10%					904.25	1.64
23	COST "B1" (Items 19 + 22)					33007.50	59.98
21	Rental Value of owned Land					14761.89	26.82
22	COST "B2" (Items 23 + 24)					47769.39	86.80
23	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	6.22	211.93	1317.48	2.39
		Female	Days	5.90	159.85	943.67	1.71
				12.12	371.78	2261.14	4.11
24	COST "C1"(Item 23+26)					35268.64	64.09
25	COST "C2"(Item 25+26)					50030.53	90.91
26	10% Cost C2*					5003.05	9.09
27	COST "C3"(Item 30+31)					55033.58	100.00
28	Yield of main produce /ha	(Rs.)		12.96	6824.26	88442.41	
29	Value of By-produce/ha.	(Rs.)		7.98	65	518.92	
						88961.33	
30	Main Produce +By produce					88961.33	
31	Per quintal cost of Prod.					4206.38	

Conclusion

The hired male and female labour utilization on small, medium and large size group was 5.8, 6.8, 6.6 days and 27.8, 25.6, 26.7 and at overall level were worked out to be 6.4 and 26.7 respectively. The utilization of bullock labour per hectare for black gram on selected farmers were 6.0, 4.9, and 5.9 pair days for small, medium and large size group respectively. The overall level was estimated at 5.6 pair days. The utilization of machinery (Hrs.) per hectare was 6.2, 7.4 and 7.6 hrs for small, medium and large size group respectively and the overall level was 7.1 hrs. The quantity of seed used was highest in large size group i.e., 16.6 kg followed by small and medium group i.e. 16.3 kg and 15.6 kg respectively. The overall level use of seed was 16.2 kg. The family male and female labour utilization on small, medium and large size group were 7.7, 6.0, 4.9 and 8.7, 5.1, 3.9 days respectively and at overall level was worked out to be 6.2 days and 5.9

days. At small farmers level, the per hectare cost of production at cost 'A₁', cost 'A₂', cost 'B₁', cost 'B₂', cost 'C₁', cost 'C₂' and cost 'C₃' were Rs.31514.12, Rs.31514.12, Rs.32781.98, Rs.47678.58, Rs.36013.78, Rs.50910.38 and Rs.56001.42 respectively. The major share of cost of cultivation goes towards cost 'A₁' (56.27 per cent). In cost A₁ share of hired labour was 13.31 per cent, bullock labour 10.62 per cent, machine charges 9.86 per cent, fertilizer 4.37 per cent, seed 3.32 per cent, plant protection 2.00 per cent, indicating that, all the above inputs are cash inputs for which farmers required to pay immediately from his pocket. The per hectare yield obtained by small farmers was 12.94 quintals with gross return of Rs. 89769.63. In case of small size group, the per quintal cost of production was Rs. 4289.95. At medium farmers level, the per hectare cost of production at cost 'A₁', cost 'A₂', cost 'B₁', cost 'B₂', cost 'C₁', cost 'C₂', cost 'C₃' were Rs. 31100.53, Rs. 31100.53, Rs. 32209.51, Rs. 46499.06, Rs.

34269.18, Rs. 48558.72 and Rs. 53414.59 respectively. The major share of cost of cultivation goes towards cost 'A₁' (58.22 per cent). In cost A₁ share of hired labour was 13.72 per cent, machine charges 12.17 per cent, bullock labour 4.98 per cent, fertilizer 3.95 per cent, seed 3.28 per cent, plant protection 1.92 per cent, indicating that, all the above inputs are cash inputs for which farmers required to pay immediately from his pocket. The per hectare yield obtained by medium farmers was 12.66 quintals. With Gross return Rs. 86127.26. The per hectare cost obtained by small farmers was Rs. 4178.60 per quintals. At large farmers level, the per hectare cost of production at cost 'A₁', cost 'A₂', cost 'B₁', cost 'B₂', cost 'C₁', cost 'C₂', cost 'C₃' were Rs.33237.36, Rs. 33237.36, Rs. 33643.00, Rs. 48733.17, Rs. 35238.16 Rs.50328.33 and Rs. 55361.16 respectively, the major share of cost of cultivation goes towards cost 'A₁' (60.04 per cent). In cost A₁ share of hired labour was 13.04 per cent, machine charges 12.16 per cent, bullock labour 10.69 per cent, seed 3.30 per cent, fertilizer 2.94 per cent, plant protection 1.77 per cent indicating that, all the above inputs are cash inputs for which farmers required to pay immediately from his pocket. The per hectare yield obtained by large farmers was 13.27 quintals with Gross return Rs. 90931.01. The per hectare cost

obtained by large farmers was Rs. 4130.22 per quintals. At overall level, the per hectare cost of production at cost 'A₁', cost 'A₂', cost 'B₁', cost 'B₂', cost 'C₁', cost 'C₂', cost 'C₃' were Rs.32103.25, Rs. 32103.25, Rs. 33007.50, Rs. 47769.39, Rs. 35268.64, Rs. 50030.53 and Rs. 55033.58 respectively. The major share of cost of cultivation goes towards cost 'A₁' (58.33 per cent). In cost A₁ share of hired labour was 13.31 per cent, machine charges 11.37 per cent, bullock labour 8.62 per cent, fertilizer 3.75 per cent, seed 3.30 per cent, plant protection 1.87 per cent indicating that, all the above inputs are cash inputs for which farmers required to pay immediately from his pocket. The per hectare yield obtained by overall farmers was 12.96 quintals with gross return of Rs. 88961.33 The per hectare cost obtained by overall farmers was Rs. 4206.38 per quintals.

The highest input output ratio at cost C₃ was recorded in large group i.e., 1.64 and the lowest input output ratio at cost C₃ was recorded in small size group. At overall level input output ratio at cost C₃ was 1.62. The input output ratio which is an indicator of economic efficiency in crop production for the crop and other discussion indicated that black gram registered a good input output ratio 1.62 means growing of the black gram is profitable venture.

Table: 5. Per hectare cost and returns from black gram cultivation

Sr. No.	Particulars		Group size			
			Small	Medium	Large	Overall
1	Yield (Qtls)	Main Produce	12.94	12.66	13.27	12.96
		By Produce	7.53	7.91	8.51	7.98
2	Price/(Qtls)	Main Produce	6899.55	6762.54	6810.69	6824.26
		By Produce	65.00	65.00	65.00	65.00
3	Value of main produce		89280.18	85613.76	90377.86	88442.41
4	Value of by-produce		489.45	514.15	553.15	518.92
5	Total produce		89769.63	86127.91	90931.01	88961.33
6	Cost of cultivation					
a)	Cost 'A ₂ '		31514.12	31100.53	33237.36	32103.25
b)	Cost 'B ₁ '		32781.98	32209.51	33643.00	33007.50
c)	Cost 'B ₂ '		47678.58	46499.06	48733.17	47769.39
	Cost 'C ₁ '		36013.78	34269.18	35238.16	35268.64
d)	Cost 'C ₂ '		50910.38	48558.72	50328.33	50030.53
e)	Cost 'C ₃ '		56001.42	53414.59	55361.16	55033.58
7	Net return over					
a)	Cost 'A ₂ '		58255.51	55027.37	57761.76	56858.08
b)	Cost 'B ₁ '		56987.65	53918.39	57356.11	55953.83
c)	Cost 'B ₂ '		42091.04	39628.85	42265.94	41191.94
	Cost 'C ₁ '		53755.85	51858.73	55760.95	53692.68
d)	Cost 'C ₂ '		38859.25	37569.19	40670.78	38930.79
e)	Cost 'C ₃ '		33768.21	32713.31	35637.95	33927.74
8	Input output ratio at					
a)	Cost 'A ₂ '		2.85	2.77	2.74	2.77
b)	Cost 'B ₁ '		2.74	2.67	2.70	2.70
c)	Cost 'B ₂ '		1.88	1.85	1.87	1.86
	Cost 'C ₁ '		2.49	2.51	2.58	2.52
d)	Cost 'C ₂ '		1.76	1.77	1.81	1.78
e)	Cost 'C ₃ '		1.60	1.61	1.64	1.62

References

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